

Leadership Culture as Determinant of Organizational Goal Attainment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

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Abstract

The paper investigated leadership culture as a determinant of organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Five research questions and five corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. The design adopted for the study is a correlational research design. The population of the study consisted of all the 278 principals in the 278 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State and the same 278 principals were drawn as the sample for the study using the purposive sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire. The first questionnaire titled "Leadership Culture Questionnaire" contained 20 questionnaire items and was used to collect data on the independent variable of the study while the other questionnaire titled "Organizational Goal Attainment Questionnaire" (OGAQ) contained 10 questionnaire items. The questionnaire was face and content validated by two lecturers in the Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rivers State. Cronbach alpha was used to estimate the reliability of the questionnaires and the reliability index of LCQ was 0.83 while that of OGAQ was 0.87. Out of the 278 copies of the questionnaire administered, 254 copies representing 91.4% were retrieved. Research questions raised were answered using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (r) while the hypotheses were tested using t -test of relationship at 0.05 level of significance.

Keywords: Culture, leadership, organizational goal attainment, Rivers State, secondary schools.

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Introduction

Secondary education is immensely significant to the advancement of any nation as it helps to bridge the shortfalls in lower education levels as well as prepare students for higher learning. Generally, the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN) (2014) as revealed in the national policy on education pointed out that secondary education is significant in the production of middle-level manpower for the nation. Similarly, the goals of secondary education as highlighted in the FRN (2013) are all about fulfilling the desire for personal development and societal growth that also

leads to development. The realization of the goals of secondary education is therefore hinged on the belief that these highlighted objectives are achievable and within the stipulated time frame. Furthermore, The FRN as cited in Etor et al., (2019:27) stated that “secondary education is expected to achieve the goals of preparing the individuals for useful living within the society, and for higher education as well as equipping secondary school leavers with the needed skills for effective living within the society”. It is only when all of these goals and objectives are met that secondary education can be termed to have attained its essence or goals.

The realization of the goals of secondary education in the school system is a responsibility assigned to different education stakeholders in the system and education goal attainment at this level depends on what they do or fail to do. Similarly, the extent to which these objectives can be achieved depends on the competence of the heads or leaders of the school starting from the principal. Principals as administrative heads of any secondary school have enormous responsibilities that are targeted towards the actualization of the earlier mentioned goals of secondary education. The activities which the principal execute day-to-day are significant to the attainment of these objectives. Educational scholars believe that it is the activities principals and other leaders in the school carry out regularly that end up becoming the culture of the leaders, followers and school in general. This implies that leadership culture is built from regular activities carried out by the leader including the principal.

In any school, there are certain practices that school heads engage in that become a norm to attain outlined educational goals and objectives and this is what translates to leadership culture in the school. Leadership culture is therefore a combination of practices attributed to leaders in the school especially the principle which guides all activities in the school for the targets of education to be attained. Supporting this dimension, Vilas-Boas et al., (2018) were of the view that in the field of leadership as a practice, in which no research has integrated the cultural dimension, leadership is seen as a cultural practice, because it understands that culture is an essential element not only for revealing and guiding how organizational practices are constructed, but it also includes how leaders make and take critical decisions, as well as how they act and interact. Leadership culture is therefore a sum of practices executed by the principal as head of the school, during his interaction with other components of the school so that outlined objectives can be attained.

Leadership must be seen as a cultural activity because it is the practices of the leader that becomes leadership culture in the long run (Pennington, Townsend & Cummins, 2003). Every leader especially the principal has their ways of interacting with various components of the school; human, material and financial and how they manage these educational resources go a long way to influence the goals that will be achieved within the period. Similarly, education researchers have asserted that leadership culture is simply the way a leader does his things such as how he interacts with people, make decisions as well as influence others. This culminates in the manner of administration in the school as well as the attainment of the goals of the school and the education sector in general. Leadership culture is a vast concept and as such comprises different practices or components. There are diverse components of a leadership culture that are instrumental to the attainment of the goals of secondary education in any society.

Similarly, educational scholars have highlighted in their opinion diverse leadership cultures that influence education across different countries. In his opinion, Guldhammer (2019) noted that leadership culture will most often include leadership skills, leadership team dimension, as well as behaviours and practices. In the same manner, other leadership experts have also incorporated practices of accountability, intra- and inter-personal relations as part of the scope of leadership culture in any formal organization which includes the school system. This implies that the leadership culture of any administrative head cuts across diverse areas of his administrative responsibility.

One of the basic cultures of a leader which is fundamental to education goal attainment is his professional skill and competence on the job. The professional skills of a leader are essential in the discharge of his day-to-day responsibilities. Leaders require several areas of skills and competence if they must be able to control the organization effectively for it to meet its goals and objectives. Piaw et al., (2014:5125) asserted that there are “five domains of leadership skill that have been associated with effective school principals were instructional leadership, cultural leadership, strategic leadership, educational management leadership and organizational management leadership”. Similarly, the leader must be able to bring in technical skill and competence among others on the job and this should be a regular practice or part of the culture of the leader for administrative effectiveness and efficiency.

In a related dimension, Knapp as cited in Bolanle (2013:27) stated that “leadership skills are “the learned ability to bring about pre-determined results with maximum certainty often with minimum use of time..., energy or both”. As such, professional skills are *sine qua non* if the leader must be able to discharge his responsibilities effectively for the attainment of the goals of the organization. Principals in like manner must show some level of continuous professional skills for the school under their headship to be able to meet its short- and long-term educational goals and objectives. Furthermore, educational experts have warned that every leader including the principals must build the leadership culture of accountability to avoid the school deviating from its intended goals and objectives. Erdag (2017:1408) stated that accountability has to do with; counting and accounting, describing or explaining, justifying, and responsibility. This simply implies that the leader must be able to report how he has utilized resources under his control, justify the reasons for doing so and take responsibility in any area of lapses. This should be a regular practice vis-à-vis the leadership culture of the principal for the school to move towards attaining its goals. Any school where the principal does not practice accountability as a leadership culture may find it difficult to make any meaningful progress educationally.

Additionally, principals must build a sound personal relationship with all educational stakeholders effortlessly in the course of discharging their responsibilities. Researchers have identified that interpersonal relations are needed to avoid burnout on the job (Rodríguez-Mantilla & Fernández-Díaz, 2017). This implies that building quality interpersonal relationships must be a continuous practice and principals must see this as an essential part of their service delivery for the attainment of the goals of the school. Interpersonal relationships

help to reduce work pressure from the principal if this is developed as a culture and makes it easy for responsibilities to be delegate and productivity increased. Principals must therefore develop a healthy leadership culture of interacting with all stakeholders including teachers, students, parents and other groups relevant to the success of the school as they have relevant roles to play in the attainment of the goals of the school.

In recent times, attention has also been given to the need for principals to mentor and coach their subordinates to improve the level of productivity in school. Rhodes as cited in Allan (2007:14) mentioned that coaching and mentoring are relevant because they aid in the transfer of learning from one person to another, resulting in greater impacts within the classroom and the potential to raise student standards and attainment. This means that a lot can be achieved in the attainment of the goals of the school if the principals cultivate the practice of coaching and mentoring. This leadership culture makes it easy for the school to function effectively and administratively even in the absence of the principal. This means that educational goals and objectives can safely be achieved if the principal gives adequate time to caching and mentoring colleagues who can contribute to the development of the school and attainment of its goals even in his absence.

Furthermore, Ali et l., (2018:508) stated that "coaching and mentoring can be 'stand-alone activities', but they can also be used to complement each other". This is because coaching is time-bound while mentoring is not although both involve a partnership of providing support to a learner. In a related dimension, other researchers agreed with Rhodes and Beneicke (2002:297) that "coaching, mentoring and peer-networking mechanisms enhance teacher professional development and performance in schools". Based on this assertion, a lot can be achieved through mentoring and coaching when the principal can groom people who will assist him on the job.

Educational researchers have conducted several studies on the contributions of leadership culture to education and its goal attainment. On their part, Nnorom and Olagbaju (2020) investigated principals' quality management skills as determinants of goal attainment in secondary schools in Ahiazu Mbaise local government area, Imo State and their study indicated that a significant relationship does exist between effective 'instructional supervision, teachers' performance evaluation and secondary school goal attainment. In a related manner, Muraina (2014) also investigated principals' managerial skills and their administrative effectiveness in schools at the secondary level in Oyo State, Nigeria and the study equally revealed that there was a significant association between principals' managerial skills and administrative effectiveness and that principals' skill on supervision had a significant relationship with their administrative effectiveness in the study area. Okotoni and Akinwale (2019) in a related instance conducted a related study on principals' communication styles and teachers' job commitment in secondary schools in Osun State, Nigeria and the study showed that aggressive communication style was negatively related to teachers' job commitment and that there was a positive relationship between open communication style and teachers' commitment to school. All of these point to the influence that the leaders' professional skills have on the administration of the school in general.

In another study, Argon (2015) examined teacher and administrator views on school principals' accountability and in the study, it was indicated that teachers and administrators ascribe the same meaning to the concept of accountability; they also believed anyone engaged in the schools should be held accountable. It was equally pointed out that school principals should not merely be responsible and accountable to their superiors but that the first and foremost reason for accountability comes from the requirement of principals to undertake their responsibilities properly and in line with established laws. The study also showed that accountability creates a positive climate in schools and that principals in Turkish education systems don't fully have the characteristics of accountability. Furthermore, Hallinger and Ko (2015) on their part investigated the need for accountability and the regression analyses found a negative impact of principal leadership practices related to strategic direction and policy environments, but there existed a positive impact on staff as well as resource management practices to enhance support for students. On their part, Himmetoğlu, et al., (2017) conducted a study on opinions of school administrators about accountability in educational organizations and the result showed that school administrators define the concept of accountability by using such terms as explaining reasons, transparency, asking for the results of assignments, the responsibility of informing, having the sense of responsibility. It was also revealed that a good school accountability system will probably have positive results such as guiding students' choice of profession, increasing success, increasing school's popularity among students and parents, revealing the present situation of the school and contributing to the modernization of the society.

On the issue of interpersonal relations, Furthermore, Nwinyokpugi and Omuakwe (2019) conducted a study on the interpersonal relationship at work; enhancing organizational productivity of deposit money banks in Port Harcourt and the study showed that workplace interpersonal relationships are also significantly related to organizational productivity in deposit money banks in Port-Harcourt. Similarly, a related study by Gemora (2014) investigated the impact of interpersonal relationships on the administrative and teaching performance among faculty administrators and the findings of the study indicated that the interpersonal skills of school administrators are very clearly evident in their support to the faculty. The school administrator ability to allow teachers a high degree of initiative and creativity in their work makes them more dedicated. Supporting the findings of this study, Charles (2017) also conducted a study on the impact of interpersonal relationships on academic performance of learners with hearing impairments focusing on St. Bernadette Turkana County, Kenya and it showed that interpersonal relationships amongst learners with hearing impairment, their parents and teachers caused improved performance through the improved language of communication, discussion group attendance, freeness in teacher-pupil approaches in discussing on subject concepts and gifts from a few parents and teachers.

Studies in other aspects of leadership culture were also carried out by researchers with relevant impacts on education goal attainment. Gettys, Martin and Bigby (2010) in their study inquired if mentoring assist in developing beginning principals' and their instructional leadership skills. It was revealed in the study that both types of mentoring programmes were

weak in creating the right support in each of the six instructional standards of instructional leadership skills. Similarly, Imo and Ekpenyong (2018) examined principals' transformational leadership practices as influencers of organizational commitment as well as value re-orientation among secondary school teachers and it showed that principals' transformational leadership practices were high, while there was a significant effect of principals' transformational leadership practices on organizational commitment and value re-orientation of teachers. Furthermore, Grover and Furnham (2016) examined coaching as a developmental intervention in organisations focusing on a systematic review of its effectiveness and the mechanisms underlying it and the study showed that coaching is an effective tool that benefits organisations and a couple of underlying facets accounted for this effectiveness while Ingersoll and Strong (2011) investigated the impact of induction and mentoring programs for beginning teachers and it was indicated that students of beginning teachers who engaged in some kind of induction possessed higher scores, or gains, on their academic achievement tests. All of these studies showed the various benefits that can be derived from adopting relevant leadership culture practices in the school.

Supporting all of these findings, Kythreotis, et al., (2010) investigated the influence of school leadership styles and culture on students' achievement in Cyprus primary schools and it showed that student achievement gains were found to be related to five factors at the school level and that relationships between effectiveness factors operating at different levels were identified. Turan and Bektas (2013) also conducted a study on the relationship between school culture and leadership practices and it was indicated that a positive and significant relationship existed between the scores of school culture and leadership practices of teachers in primary education. On their part, Quin et al., (2015) examined the correlation between leadership, culture, and student achievement and the study showed a significant association between leadership practices and school culture as well as school culture and student achievement but no relationship was established between leadership practices and school culture.

All of the studies conducted by these various researchers point to the fact that what constitutes the leadership practice of any principal has a significant effect on the administration of the school which is related to the goals of secondary education. Therefore, any principal who must succeed in the attainment of educational goals and objectives in the school where he heads must be careful in developing the right leadership culture as this will go a long way to influence all education-related activities in the school as well as contribute to the attainment of the goals of education in the school both in the short and long term.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate leadership culture as a determinant of organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. In specific terms, the specific objectives of the study were to:

1. identify if the professional skills of leaders as a determinant of organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

2. examine if leaders' accountability is a determinant of organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State
3. determine if leaders' interpersonal relations is a determinant of organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State
4. ascertain if leaders coaching and mentoring is a determinant of organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State
5. identify if leadership culture is a determinant of organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Research questions

The following research questions were answered in the study:

1. What is the relationship between leaders' professional skills and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between leaders' accountability and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
3. What is the relationship between leaders' interpersonal relations and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
4. What is the relationship between leaders' coaching and mentoring and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
5. What is the joint relationship between leadership culture and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between leaders' professional skills and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State
2. There is no significant association between leaders' accountability and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State
3. There is no significant association between leaders' interpersonal relations and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State
4. There is no significant association between leaders coaching and mentoring and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State
5. There is no significant joint association between leadership culture and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Methods

The design employed for the study is correlation and this was because the study intends to investigate the strength of the relationship between a dependent and an independent variable. The population of the study comprised all the 278 principals in the 278 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The purposive sampling technique was used to select all these 278

principals as the sample for the study and this was because the population of the study is very small. Two different questionnaires were designed as an instrument for data collection. The questionnaires had two sections namely; Part A and Part B. Part A was used to collect demographic information about the respondents of the study while Part B contained the questionnaire items. The first questionnaire titled "Leadership Culture Questionnaire" contained 20 questionnaire items and was used to collect data on the independent variable of the study while the other questionnaire titled "Organizational Goal Attainment Questionnaire" (OGAQ) contained 10 questionnaire items. The questionnaires were answered on a four-point modified Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) with weighted values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instrument was face and content validated by two lecturers in the Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rivers State. Cronbach alpha was used to estimate the reliability of the questionnaires and the reliability index of LCQ was 0.83 while that of OGAQ was 0.87. The questionnaires were administered by the researcher with the help of three trained research assistants who were oriented on how to distribute the instrument and how to retrieve and collate the responses. Out of the 278 copies of the questionnaire administered, 254 copies representing 91.4% were retrieved and used for data analysis. The research questions were answered using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (r) while the hypotheses were tested using a t-test of relationship at 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Answer to Research Questions

Research question 1

What is the relationship between leaders' professional skills and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State? In table 1, it was revealed that the value of r was -0.04 and this indicated that there existed a low negative relationship between leaders' professional skills and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Similarly, the value of r^2 of 0.0016 implied that leaders' professional skills only contributed 0.16% of organizational goal attainment while the other percentage is contributed by other factors.

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (r) of the Relationship between Leaders' Professional Skills and Organizational Goal Attainment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Variable	n	r	r^2	Remark
Leaders Professional Skills Organizational Goal Attainment	254	-0.04	0.0016	Low negative relationship

Research question 2

What is the relationship between leaders' accountability and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State? Table 2 showed that the value of r was 0.88 and this implied that there existed a very strong positive relationship between leaders' accountability and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Similarly, the value of r^2 of 0.7744 indicated that leaders' accountability accounted for about 77.4% of organizational goal attainment while other factors account for the remaining percentage.

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (r) of the Relationship between Leaders' Accountability and Organizational Goal Attainment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Variable	n	r	r^2	Remark
Leaders Accountability	254	0.88	0.7744	A very strong positive relationship
Organizational Goal Attainment				

Research question 3

What is the relationship between leaders' interpersonal relations and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State? In table 3, the value of r of 0.65 indicated that a strong positive relationship existed between leaders' interpersonal relationship and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State while on the other hand, the value of r^2 of 0.4225 implied that leaders' interpersonal relations account for 42.2% of organizational goal attainment and the remaining percentage were as a result of other factors aside from the leaders' interpersonal relations.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (r) of the Relationship between Leaders' Accountability and Organizational Goal Attainment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Variable	n	r	r^2	Remark
Leaders Interpersonal Relations	254	0.65	0.4225	Strong positive relationship
Organizational Goal Attainment				

Research question 4

What is the relationship between leaders' coaching and mentoring and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State? In table 4, it was revealed that the value of r of 0.86 meant that there existed a very strong positive relationship between leaders' coaching and mentoring and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Similarly, the value of r^2 of 0.7396 implied that leaders' coaching and mentoring accounted for about 74% of organizational goal attainment in public secondary schools in River State while the remaining percentage was as a result of other factors.

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (r) of the Relationship between Leaders' Coaching and Mentoring and Organizational Goal Attainment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Variable	n	r	r ²	Remark
Leaders Coaching and Mentoring	254	0.86	0.7396	A very strong positive relationship
Organizational Goal Attainment				

Research question 5

What is the joint relationship between leadership culture and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State? The value of r^2 of 1.000 in table 5 indicated that the joint relationship of leaders' professional skills, accountability, interpersonal relations and coaching and mentoring accounts for about 100% of organizational goal attainment in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 5: Regression analysis of the joint relationship between leadership culture and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
1	1.000 ^a	1.000		1.000	.00000

a. Predictors: (Constant), VAR00004, VAR00001, VAR00003, VAR00002

Test of hypotheses

Hypothesis one

There is no significant association between leaders' professional skills and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. In table 6, it was revealed that at 0.05 level of significance and 252 degrees of freedom, the value of t-cal. of 0.63 was less than the value of t-crit. of 1.96 and as such the null hypothesis was not rejected indicating that there was no significant association between leaders' professional skills and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 6: Summary of t-test of Relationship between Leaders' Professional Skills and Organizational Goal Attainment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Variable	n	df	t-cal.	t-crit.	Level of significance	Decision
Leaders Professional Skills	254	252	0.63	1.96	0.05	H ₀ was not rejected
Organizational Goal Attainment						

Hypothesis two

There is no significant association between leaders' accountability and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Table 7 indicated that at 0.05 level of significance and 252 degrees of freedom, the value of t-cal. of 29.47 was above the value of t-crit. of 1.96 and as such the null hypothesis was rejected implying that there was a

significant association between leaders' accountability and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 7: Summary of t-test of Relationship between Leaders' Accountability and Organizational Goal Attainment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Variable	n	df	t-cal.	t-crit.	Level of significance	Decision
Leaders Accountability Organizational Goal Attainment	254	252	29.47	1.96	0.05	H ₀ was rejected

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant association between leaders' interpersonal relations and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Table 8 revealed that at 0.05 level of significance and 252 degrees of freedom, the value of t-cal. of 13.58 was above the value of t-crit. of 1.96 and as such the null hypothesis was rejected meaning that there was a significant association between leaders' interpersonal relations and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 8: Summary of t-test of Relationship between Leaders' Interpersonal Relations and Organizational Goal Attainment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Variable	n	df	t-cal.	t-crit.	Level of significance	Decision
Leaders Interpersonal Relations Organizational Goal Attainment	254	252	13.58	1.96	0.05	H ₀ was rejected

Hypothesis 4

There is no significant association between leaders coaching and mentoring and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. In table 9, at 0.05 level of significance and 252 degrees of freedom, the value of t-cal. of 26.79 was above the value of t-crit. of 1.96 and as such the null hypothesis was rejected and this meant that there was a significant association between leaders coaching and mentoring and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 9: Summary of t-test of Relationship between Leaders' Coaching and Mentoring and Organizational Goal Attainment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Variable	n	df	t-cal.	t-crit.	Level of significance	Decision
Leaders Coaching and Mentoring Organizational Goal Attainment	254	252	26.79	1.96	0.05	H ₀ was rejected

Hypothesis 5

There is no significant joint relationship between leadership culture and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Table 10 showed that at 0.05 level of significance, and 4 by 249 degrees of freedom, the p-value of 0.00 was less than the alpha level of 0.05 and as such, the null hypothesis was rejected indicating that there was a significant joint relationship between leadership culture and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 10: ANOVA Output of a multiple linear regression analysis of Relationship between Leadership Culture and Organizational Goal Attainment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	166.996	4	41.749	5.565	.000
	Residual	.000	249	.000		
	Total	166.996	253			

a. Dependent Variable: VAR00005

b. Predictors: (Constant), VAR00004, VAR00001, VAR00003, VAR00002

Discussion

Leaders' professional skills and organizational goal attainment

The result of the study indicated that the value of r of -0.04 suggested that a low and negative relationship between leaders' professional skills and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Similarly, there was no significant association between leaders' professional skills and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This finding agrees with the findings of a related study conducted by Nnorom and Olagbaju (2020) which revealed that a significant relationship does exist between effective 'instructional supervision, teachers' performance evaluation and secondary school goal attainment. This implies that the inability to properly manage the skills acquired by leaders in the school can negatively affect the attainment of educational goals and objectives.

Professional skills ought to contribute to the ability of leaders to discharge their responsibilities professionally. However, it is one thing to acquire a skill and it is another thing to put it to use especially for the attainment of the goals of the organization. In his study, Muraina (2014) indicated that there was a significant relationship that existed between principals' managerial skills and their administrative effectiveness and that principals' supervision skills showed a significant relationship with their administrative effectiveness in the study area. This means that when leaders put the skills they acquire to use, they can make a meaningful impact on the attainment of the goals and objectives of the organization where they operate.

Principals as leaders need to develop the habit of engaging their acquired skills in the pursuit and attainment of the goals of the organization. Principals must learn how to put acquired skills into professional use just as they learn to acquire the skills. Leaders should be able to understand where and why they must put their acquired skills to use as this will affect the realization of the goals of the school. Supporting this perception, Okotoni and Akinwale (2019) in their study indicated that aggressive communication style was negatively related to teachers' job commitment and that there was a positive relationship between open communication style and teachers' commitment to the school. This means that professional skills are not enough in the attainment of the goals of any organization but the utilization of these skills are instrumental to the attainment of the goals and objectives of the organization.

Leaders' accountability and organizational goal attainment

The responses from the respondents of the study showed that with the value of r which was 0.88, there existed a very strong positive relationship between leaders' accountability and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Similarly, there was a significant association between leaders' accountability and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study by Argon (2015) agrees with this finding as it was revealed that a principals' accountability practice helps to build a positive climate in schools. Therefore, being accountable is as important as any other educational practice if principals must assist the school to achieve its goals.

Accountable principals take responsibility for their actions and give proper direction where necessary. Hallinger and Ko (2015) in their study supported this assertion by pointing out that a positive impact of staff management and resource management practices in terms of enhancing support for students existed in the study. This is important because an accountable leader is not only transparent but must learn to judiciously utilize human and material resources at his or her disposal for the success of the organization.

Educational researchers have also identified the fact that accountability enables a leader to be able to report or give feedback for all responsibilities entrusted into his hand. An accountable leader also considers the goals of the organization and this is essential for the success of the organization as a whole. Himmetoğlu, et al. (2017) in their study clarified this position by pointing out from their study that school administrators saw accountability as transparency, asking for the results of assignments, the responsibility of informing, having the sense of responsibility. They also asserted that a good school accountability system has a positive effect such as guiding students' choice of profession, increasing success, increasing school's popularity among students and parents, revealing the present situation of the school and contributing to the modernization of the society. This explains why the study revealed that leaders' accountability as a leadership culture significantly and positively contributes to the attainment of organizational goals and objectives in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Leaders' interpersonal relations and organizational goal attainment

In the study, it was revealed that the value of r of 0.65 showed that a strong positive relationship existed between leaders' interpersonal relationships and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Furthermore, there existed a significant association between leaders' interpersonal relations and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This finding agrees with the outcome of a similar study carried out by Nwinyokpugi and Omunakwe (2019) which showed that workplace interpersonal relationships significantly influenced organizational productivity in deposit money banks in Port Harcourt. This is similar to the outcome of the study which also revealed that interpersonal relations positively influence organizational goal attainment in schools in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Interpersonal relations are essential as it helps to improve on the quality and quantity of goals that can be achieved at any particular point in time.

Principals who build interpersonal relations as part of their leadership culture are simply expanding their scope of influence making it easy for more goals and objectives to be achieved at any particular point in time. In a supporting study, Gemora (2014) investigated the influence of interpersonal relationships on the administrative and teaching performance among faculty administrators and the findings of the study indicated that the interpersonal skills of school administrators are very clearly evident in their support to the faculty. This implies that the essence of every interpersonal relationship must be clearly defined to avoid the abuse of such a relationship which can be counterproductive to the attainment of the goals of the organization.

Interpersonal relations enable the principal to be able to delegate responsibilities which make goals easily and effectively achieved in any organization. Charles (2017) supported this assertion by revealing from the findings of his study that interpersonal relationships amongst students with hearing impairment, their parents and teachers led to improved performance through the improved language of communication, attendance of discussion group, freeness in teacher-pupil approaches in deliberating on subject concepts and gifts from some parents and teachers. Interpersonal relations developed by the principal as part of his leadership culture has an unlimited influence on the administration of the school generally and the attainment of organizational goals in the school.

Leaders' coaching and mentoring and organizational goal attainment

From the responses of the principals sampled for the study, the value of r of 0.86 meant that there existed a very strong positive relationship between leaders' coaching and mentoring and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. In a related manner, there was a significant association between leaders coaching and mentoring and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Agreeing with this position, Grover and Furnham (2016) noted in their study that coaching is an effective tool that benefits organisations and several underlying facets contribute to this effectiveness.

Coaching and mentoring contributes to the grooming of competent employees who will contribute to the sustainability of any organization.

In most formal organizations, coaching and mentoring is used to develop the future employees of the organization who will also support the attainment of the goals and objectives of the organization. Gettys, Martin and Bigby (2010) in their study inquired if mentoring assists in developing beginning principals' instructional leadership skills and it was revealed in the study that both types of mentoring programmes were weak in providing the appropriate support in each of the six instructional standards of instructional leadership skills. Therefore, school administrators must ensure that they are being mentored by other experts so that they can in turn groom another set of employees who will contribute to the attainment of the goals and objectives of the organization in the long run.

Similarly, principals as leaders need to ensure that the employees they coach or mentor under the policies and practices of the organization as this will enable them to put the skills' they acquire to use for the attainment of the goals and objectives of the organization. Supporting this idea, Imo and Ekpenyong (2018) the leadership system of any principal must be able to bring about value reorientation and this is instrumental for advancing the goals and objectives of any organization. Practices like this will make it easy for the leader to accomplish more and better educational goals in the long run.

Leadership culture and organizational goal attainment

In the study, the value of r^2 of 1.000 pointed to the fact that the joint relationship of leaders' professional skills, accountability, interpersonal relations and coaching and mentoring accounts for about 100% of organizational goal attainment in public secondary schools in Rivers State. In the same manner, there was a significant joint relationship between leadership culture and organizational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This means that a combination of the right leadership culture practices will go a long way to contribute to the attainment of the goals of secondary education in public secondary schools in Rivers State with ease. Supporting this perception, Kythreotis, et al., (2010) in their study found that student achievement gains were found to be related with five factors at the school level and that relationships between effectiveness factors operating at different levels were identified and this included the culture of the school which the principal is also a major contributor. Furthermore, Turan and Bektas (2013) in their study on the relationship between school culture and leadership practices indicated that a positive and significant relationship existed between the scores of school culture and leadership practices of teachers in primary education. It can therefore be deduced that healthy school culture, as well as quality leadership culture among school administrators, is fundamental to the attainment of educational goals at any level of education.

Leadership culture is all about how a principal handles his responsibilities and if this is efficiently and effectively discharged, the school will not find it difficult to meet its objectives. Quin et al., (2015) in their study supported this idea as they revealed in their study that there

was a significant correlation between leadership practices and school culture and school culture and student achievement but no relationship was established between leadership practices and school culture. The leadership culture control what happens in the school and this is necessary for the success of the school as a system. On their part, Ingersoll and Strong (2011) noted that there are gains that can be benefited if the right leadership culture practices are instituted in any school and this is an aspect that school administrators need to pay attention to for the attainment of the goals and objectives of secondary education in public schools in Rivers State.

Conclusion

The study concluded that there existed a significant association between leadership culture components of leaders' professional skills, accountability, interpersonal relations and coaching and mentoring on organisational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Leadership professional skills and interpersonal relations had a high positive relationship on organisational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers while accountability and coaching and mentoring had a low positive relationship on organisational goal attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers.

Recommendations

In line with the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Principals and other leaders in secondary schools in Rivers State should be exposed to essential organisational skills through regular training that will enable them to contribute further to the attainment of organizational goals and objectives. Conferences, seminars and workshops should be organized regularly for these leaders in key areas of professional skills need to enable them to contribute effectively to the attainment of the goals of secondary education in Rivers State.
2. The government should endeavour to formulate policies that will make school leaders accountable for their actions, programmes and other resources under their custody. This will help to ensure that the authority, privileges and other resources entrusted into the hand of the principal are used judiciously for the attainment of the goals and objectives of secondary education in Rivers State.
3. The principal and other administrative heads in the school should engage in regular social gathering activities such as regular briefing, recreation among others. This will provide an opportunity for proper bonding and sharing of ideas that will help to improve the attainment of the goals of secondary education in Rivers State.
4. Coaching and mentorship programmes should be encouraged in secondary schools in Rivers State as this will provide an opportunity for sharing and delegation of responsibilities which will promote the furtherance of the goals and objectives of secondary education in Rivers State.

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5. The leadership culture established in the school should be clearly defined and communicated to all members of the school. This will make it easy for actions to be taken even in the absence of the head in the school as clearly defined policies, rules and regulations will make it easy for actions to be taken that will contribute to goal attainment in the school.

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